

A Cross-Cultural Investigation of Emotional Responses to Architecture in the Era of Terror

Gali Zilbershtein, Department of Architecture, Texas A&M University – USA

Andrew D. Seidel, Department of Architecture, Texas A&M University – USA

Abstract

The current knowledge, concerning the influence of architectural and social environments on people's emotional responses of personal security, addresses mainly threats of 'conventional' crimes, and relatively ignores threats associated with the recent proliferation of terrorism. This study attempts to address this gap by examining two basic questions:

- (a) Do threats of terrorism as compared to threats of conventional crime lead to different perceptual and emotional responses to features of the built environment?
- (b) Are these differences in perceptions of security mediated by cultural contexts?

The study introduces a new rigorous experimental methodology to test the two questions. The experiment includes manipulation of architectural and social qualities of the setting as well as the contextual threat (terror or crime). Furthermore, the experiment was administered in two cultural environments that differ in their actual exposure to terrorism (US and Israel).

The preliminary findings suggest that differences in threats (crime and terror) intervene in the way the architecture and social cues affect feeling of security. Moreover, while the Americans and Israelis responded similarly to the examined environmental features in a manipulated context of conventional crime, they reacted differently in the context of terror related threat. The findings suggest that fear of conventional crime is rooted in humans and thus may be similar in different populations. The fear of terrorism, on the other hand, is new to people and therefore relies on the level of habituation of the specific society to a terror stricken reality.

Keywords: Emotional responses, terror, crime, architecture, built environment, perception of security.

Introduction

There is research to suggest that until very recently the culture of architects around the world has usually ignored terrorism as a factor to be addressed in the design of buildings. Seidel and Ozdil's study, conducted prior to September 11, 2001, surveyed practicing architects from the United Kingdom, the United States and Australasia on "the knowledge areas they report are needed for successful design". This comprehensive study does not indicate terrorism, nor security in general, as aspects architects reported themselves to be involved with in their work. Since 2001, the concern from and interest in terrorism, has greatly increased. This recent trend is manifested in the numerous publications that claim to address how to gear the built environment against the threat of terrorism (c.f. Demkin and Blumgart 2001; Demkin 2004; FEMA 2003; GSA 2003; Wright 2002, 2003). Perhaps these publications are now

improving how architects understand terrorism. However, it should be noted that the quality of all these publications is yet to be determined. Many are heavily anecdotal without a thorough research underpinning. And, some say, they try to deal with terrorism as if they were trying to predict the “unthinkable” (Bracken, 2001).

The recent proliferation of terrorism projects a clear picture of a reality in which absolute personal security is an unfeasible idea. Facing this threat, the design of the built environment has to attend more thoroughly to the psycho-emotional needs of security (Kitchen 2001). The present paper provides a preliminary examination of the question of whether architects, at this day and age, need to address the old task of designing for emotional comfort in renewed formats or whether they should follow existing theories which relate primarily to crime prevention.

One of the greatest challenges the architectural realm faces is to provide the users of the built environment with comfortable designs. One dimension of comfort is physical: when design provides conditions adequate to activities, and acts as a line of defense for the human body (Saarinen 1976). The second dimension of comfort is psycho-emotional (Holahan 1982; Stamps 1997), that is, the design makes people feel pleased. There are many aspects to this emotional pleasure and they involve issues of aesthetics, satisfaction with the effectiveness of the design to comply with functional or social needs, and feeling safe and protected in the built environment. These different aspects of the psycho-emotional comfort are interrelated, and both physical and psycho-emotional comforts are inherently associated with aspects of security (Saarinen 1976).

Well-acknowledged theories and empirical studies further substantiate the significance of humans’ emotional needs in the context of the built environment. According to evolutionary perspectives, evaluation of surroundings is vital to humans’ existence (Kaplan, Kaplan and Ryan 1998; Nasar 1997; Nasar and Jones 1997). People’s attitudes and responses towards the physical environment (Holahan 1982), including their perceptions of safety (Barker and Page 2002), affect their behavior, as well as their physical and mental well-being (Ulrich, Simons, Losito, Fiorito, Miles and Zelson 1991; Ulrich, 1993).

With the significance of the subject in mind, a closer look at the existing theories concerning security and its perception reveal that these theories address the concern of ‘conventional’,

person-to-person crime and relatively ignore the threat of terrorism. These theories mostly relate to the prevention of crime through the tactic of deterrence (Jacobs 1961; Newman 1972; Tijerino 1998). In these theories, the feeling of security is based on whether the users of the environment perceive it as deterring potential offenders or as providing opportunity for committing a crime. These issues of deterrence as well as the conditions that elicit a threat seem to differ when we come to consider terrorism. Terrorism varies from any other crime in the risks the offenders are willing to take as well as their goals, their means and incentives. Consequently, it is plausible to assume that the environmental physical attributes that induce or discourage terror differ from environmental conditions that affect threats of 'conventional' crime.

In addition, evolutionary perspectives make a case for a basic difference between the two threats (terrorism and crime) in their relation to people. According to these perspectives, people are biologically prepared to deal with situations that were either beneficial or threatening to the survival of pre-modern humans (Ulrich et al. 1991). Following this notion, threats of conventional crime have been paralleled in literature to predatory threats, while no pre-modern equivalent was ever suggested in the case of terrorism threats.

The discussion thus far highlights the need to look into the differences between threats of terrorism and threats of conventional crime in their relation to the users of the built environment. Consequently, this study sets to examine this issue on two levels:

- (a) A practical level: Do threats of terrorism and threats of conventional crime lead to different perceptual and emotional responses to features of the built environment?
- (b) A basic, theoretical level: Are these differences in perceptions of security mediated by cultural contexts?

Literature review

In order to further substantiate the need for this study and to reason its specific research hypotheses, a more detailed examination of the literature is hereby presented. The following will provide a closer look into the evolutionary perspectives as well as to the built environment and its relation to threats and human responses.

Theories of evolution posit that humans' evaluation of their surroundings is a principle of existence. In order to survive, humans have always had to assess whether events or circumstances might benefit or threaten their well-being (Nasar 1997). This notion co-exists with the idea of the environment as a source of information (Kaplan et al. 1998).

In addition, evolutionary perspectives often contend that people today are to some extent biologically prepared to deal with situations that were either beneficial or threatening to the survival of pre-modern humans (Ulrich et al. 1991). Ulrich (1993) distinguishes between two types of 'preparedness': biophilic (positive) and biophobic (negative) responses to certain natural stimuli and their configuration. Studies have proven that these responses, besides being affecting the liking of a scene, have meaningful implications on people's level of well-being. This impact on the level of well-being is expressed through the change in a person's level of stress and the level of high-order cognitive functioning (Ulrich 1993).

Orians's (1980, 1986; Ulrich 1993) 'savanna phenomenon' provides a good illustration of humans' search for environments that diminish threats. It also exemplifies the pre-modern roots of modern humans' preferences. According to Orians, savanna environments, compared to other habitats, provided favorable combinations of primary necessities to early humans. Savannas offered more abundant plant and animal food as well as lower risk. The lower risk in the savanna stemmed from the particular physical configuration of such a space: Visual openness, escape opportunities (Appleton 1975), surveillance (Appleton 1975), and lower probabilities to encounter close hidden predatory threats (Ulrich 1993). These physical attributes of the savannas are the same as the elements that comprise the basics for crime prevention theories in the modern communities. In fact, several empirical studies (Ulrich 1993) have shown that today, people from different origins and ages around the world prefer (like) environments that are savanna like in appearance (Rabinowitz and Coughlin 1970; Ruiz and Bernaldez 1982).

Peoples' security related responses to environmental stimuli have been analyzed in the literature along two levels: distal and proximate (Nasar and Jones 1997). The distal level addresses a general worry about the chance of victimization. This worry is associated (among other things) to the symbolic sense of a place, i.e., the type of building and especially the context in which it operates (Lang 1987; Nasar 1997). The proximate level is linked to the search of particular cues that may evoke specific fears. This level relates to either the formal,

structural cues of the surroundings (Lang, 1987; Nasar, 1997) or to social cues that can be detected in a place. The study described here sets to follow the distal and proximate analysis of Nasar and Jones (1997).

In consideration of factors that are associated with the distal level, this study addresses two variables. The first of the two is the threat context - that of terrorism and that of conventional crime. These two categories of threat affect the security context of a place and the general chance, and hence - worry of victimization. The second variable of the distal level is the specific architectural environment that is associated with a specific building type. In this case, only one particular variant is explored. Specifically, the study focuses on the entrance to a public building in daylight during business hours. The focus on an entrance is due to its fundamental role in forming a perception of a building by providing one of the first experiences a person has with a facility. In addition, as history has shown, securing all access is a main strategy for the defense; and indeed, in today's world, access control at an entrance is considered a main mechanism for securing a structure (Demkin and Blumgart 2001). Considering that "Images help humans to quickly identify objects, predict what will happen, evaluate consequences, and act" (Kaplan 1973 cited in Nasar and Jones 1997), people's initial perception of a building (as affected by viewing the entrance) may determine their behaviors by attracting them to use the facility or discouraging them from doing so. The issue of attraction/repulsion and its connection to feelings of safety is further addressed in the study's variables at the proximate level.

With the intention of simplification, the study examines one of each of the types of cues that are included in the proximate level (one structural cue and one social cue) as basic examples to those groups of cues. The examined structural cue addresses the complex notion of mystery, which is considered in the literature as one of the key attributes affecting feelings of security as well as levels of attraction/repulsion. A mysterious place, one that presents concealed elements or some kind of a curve in a person's path, can contribute both to the fear of danger and to an attraction to that environment. Herzog and Miller (1998: 430) qualify this ambiguous proposition and state, "humans typically are attracted to dangerous situations up to a point, but beyond that point, attraction turns into fear as the danger becomes too salient or immediate". The examined social cue in the study relates to the mere presence/absence of people in a place. Previous studies show that presence of other people in a scene increases the feeling of security (Shaffer and Anderson 1983). This pattern is accounted by the notion of

“natural surveillance”, where the presence of others serves as a threat to the potential offender (Nasar and Jones 1997).

Derivations & specific research hypotheses

Congruent with the notion of the distal level, the study assumes that different threat contexts (crime and terror), as well as different cultural contexts (one that is accustomed to terror and one that is not), mediate differently the effects of the built environment on personal feelings of security. In order to test these arguments the study presents and examines the following four hypotheses:

- (1) Threats of terror lead to more fear than threats of ‘conventional’ crime.
- (2) When terrorism is not a threat, people are more attracted to use a public building when the view of the entrance from the direction they are approaching is partially concealed. When terrorism threat is present people are more attracted to use the building when the entrance (including doors and security measures) is fully revealed.

The second hypothesis is based on literature regarding the effects of “environmental mystery” on humans’ reactions (Herzog and Miller 1998). In the present study, the environmental representation of mystery is the extent to which the building’s entrance is fully exposed or partially concealed. When there is no threat of terrorism, people prefer scenes that portray some sense of mystery and are congruent with the human urge to explore (Kaplan et al. 1998). In contrast, when the threat of terrorism exists, people prefer conditions that support their need to understand the situation at hand (Kaplan et al. 1998).

- (3) Presence of many people at the entrance of a public building evokes positive feeling of security among people that are approaching the building when terrorism is not a threat, while the same social quality evokes feeling of insecurity when terrorism is a threat.

When terrorism is not a threat, the notion of “natural surveillance” deters potential criminals and gives confidence to the user of the environment. However, in the context of a terrorism threat, potential terrorists are often not deterred by the risk of being caught or killed.

Moreover, since crowded places present an opportunity for maximum destruction or harm, the presence of many people may in fact increase the danger and thereby lower the perceived personal safety.

- (4) Due to different levels of habituation to a terror stricken reality, members of different societies may perceive and react differently to physical and social cues. Such societal differences in security / safety perception are not expected in relation to threat of crime.

Concurrent with the evolutionary perspective, the danger and the consequential fear of conventional, person-to-person crime correspond to the old hazard of being attacked by predators. This association is reinforced by crime prevention theories common all over the world that seek to provide physical conditions that resemble characteristics of savanna setting. In contrast, the first part of the hypothesis focuses on the threat of terrorism, which is relatively new to mankind, and therefore people are not in any way biologically prepared for it. That is why our perception of security in this situation is mostly based on personal experience, i.e., individual learning, that occurs within a given society.

Method

An experimental design was employed to test the hypotheses regarding the differences in perception of security in the built environment under different contexts (threat of terrorism / no threat of terrorism). The within-group factorial design included the manipulation of three factors:

- (1) The threat: Terrorism threat or absence of such a threat, when the only threat is of 'conventional' crime. This factor was manipulated through two written scenarios that described two different realities. Subjects were asked to place themselves in each of the stories (see full versions of the scenarios in Appendix A).
- (2) Physical factor: The level of the concealment of the entrance, manipulated by the angle from which the photo was taken. A frontal picture produced an image in which the doors and the security arrangements were fully revealed, while a side image set conditions in which the doors and the security arrangements were concealed.

- (3) Social factor: Presence/absence of crowds at the scene. The presence or absence of people in the photos was manipulated by computer-generated graphics.

The dependent variables of this study were self-reported responses, directed at the perception of personal safety associated with the entrances of the buildings. Participants expressed their emotional responses to a condition by answering the question “How safe would you feel entering the building?” (on an eleven points scale, ranging from zero, very unsafe, to ten, very safe).

Two groups (ten subjects each) from two different cultural / societal settings (US and Israel) participated in this study. Entrances to two public buildings from Bryan-College Station area were picked to serve as a replication factor in the study. Photos of the two entrances were manipulated in order to provide the necessary visual stimuli for this study (see Figure 1).

Figure 1A, with concealment & with people.

Figure 1B, with concealment & with people.

Figure 1C, with concealment & no people.

Figure 1D, with concealment & no people.

Figure 1E, no concealment & with people.

Figure 1F, no concealment & with people.

Figure 1G, no concealment & no people.

Figure 1H, no concealment & no people.

Figure 1A-H, the visual stimuli of the study.

Results

The findings of this preliminary study offer substantial support to the general research hypotheses. In addition, the findings also provide credence to the research design that was employed in this case.

The threat factor had the major main-effect influencing both Americans as well as Israelis in their ratings of feelings of safety [Americans $F(1,9)=24.261$, $P<0.01$; Israelis $F(1,9)=6.953$, $P<0.03$]. Both samples felt safer when there was no terrorism threat. In the context of no terrorism threat, the two samples were similar in their ratings of feeling of safety (Americans $M=7.46$; Israelis $M=7.48$). Under the threat of terrorism, Israelis felt safer ($M=6.15$) than Americans ($M=5.213$). These results support both hypothesis 1 as well as hypothesis 4.

Hypothesis 2 concerning the interaction of the threat with the concealment level of the entrance was not supported by the findings. When terror threat was present, Israelis felt safer when an entrance was partially concealed ($M=6.45$) than fully revealed ($M=5.85$). Israelis felt safer with a concealed entrance even when terrorism threat was introduced. However, the difference in this case was much smaller ($M=7.55$ vs. $M=7.4$). The Americans' perception of safety was not influenced significantly by the interaction of the concealment factor with threat.

Hypothesis 3 that addresses the interaction of the threat factor with the social factor is supported in the Israeli sample, while the results of the American sample, only partially support it. As illustrated in Figure 2, under terrorism threat, Israelis felt safer when no people were at the scene of the entrance ($M=6.48$), than when people were present ($M=5.82$). When there was no threat of terrorism, Israelis reported higher feeling of safety when there were people at the scene ($M=7.88$ vs. $M=7.08$). Results of the American sample, presented in Figure 3, reveal that when there was no terrorism threat (but only 'conventional' crime threat) presence of people at a scene increased feeling of security significantly (with people $M=8.000$; no people $M=6.925$). In the context of terrorism threat, presence of people at a scene did not influence Americans' feeling of security (with people $M=5.300$, no people $M=5.125$).

Figure 2, Israeli's reported safety as affected by threat & presence of people

Figure 3, American’s reported safety as affected by threat & presence of people

General discussion & conclusion

Two basic questions are addressed in this study: Whether the relatively new threat of terrorism should be perceived in the same light of conventional crime or whether this threat introduces a new qualitative change in the relation of architecture and people’s perceptions of security; and whether different cultural contexts (one that is accustomed to terror and one that is not) mediate differently the effects of the built environment on personal feelings of security.

The findings clearly support the main hypotheses of this study (hypotheses 1, 4), which state that: fear of terrorism is greater than the fear of conventional crime; and that fear of terrorism threat is not the same all over the world, while fear of conventional crime (in absence of terrorism threat) is similar among different populations.

Findings also illustrate a central difference between emotional responses to features of the environment under the two different contexts of threats. Moreover, the findings of the Israeli sample support hypothesis 3, i.e., show significant differences in the perception of personal security as affected by the interaction of threat factor and social factor.

While considering the findings of this study and their theoretical and practical implications, it is important to make the following cautionary notes.

Since hypothesis 2 was not supported by the findings, it is possible that the underlying assumption of it is wrong; and that the factor of concealment affects positively perception of security under the different threats. However, it may also be suggested that the change of direction or view of the entrance that was intended to create the two situations (with / without concealment) was a too subtle manipulation in this study. Therefore, the issue of concealment requires further and deeper investigation.

The fact that this study was done as a preliminary examination of the subject, conducted as a within group design and included a very small number of nonrandom participants, restricts the findings and analysis from becoming conclusive evidence. Yet, the current results are pointing into a new direction and insight in the search for architectural solutions in the era of terror. The findings suggest that fear of conventional crime is rooted in humans and thus may be similar in different populations. The fear of terrorism, on the other hand, is new to people and therefore relies on the level of habituation of the specific society to a terror stricken reality. Considering that this study is only a first step in this puzzle, a further and more extended study of the two populations as well as other groups and other environmental conditions is therefore warranted.

REFERENCES

Appleton, Jay. 1975. *The experience of landscape*. London: Wiley.

Bracken, Paul. 2001. "Rethinking the unthinkable: New priorities for new national security." In *The age of terror - America and the world after September 11*, edited by Strobe Talbott and Chanda, Nayan, 171-192. New York: Basic Books & Yale Center for the Study of Globalization.

Barker, Michael and Stephen Page. 2002. "Visitor safety in urban tourism environments: The case of Auckland, New Zealand." *Cities*, 19 (4): 273-282.

Demkin, Joseph A. and Pamela J. Blumgart, eds. 2001. *Building security through design*. Washington, DC: AIA.

Demkin, Joseph A., ed. 2004. *Security planning and design: A guide for architects and building design professionals*. Hoboken, New Jersey: John Wiley & Sons, Inc.

FEMA. 2003. *Primer for design of commercial buildings to mitigate terrorist attacks*. US Department of Homeland Security, Federal Emergency Management Agency.

General Services Administration (GSA). 2003. *P100-2003: Facilities standards for the public buildings service (PBS)*. USA: GSA.

Herzog, Thomas R. and Edward J. Miller. 1998. "The role of mystery in perceived danger and environmental preference." *Environment and Behavior*, 30 (4): 429-449.

Holahan, Charles J. 1982. *Environmental psychology*. New York: Random House.

Jacobs, Jane. 1961. *The death and life of great American cities*. New York: Vintage.

Kaplan, Rachel, Stephen Kaplan and Robert L. Ryan. 1998. *With people in mind*. Washington, DC: Island Press.

Kaplan, Stephen. 1973. "Cognitive maps in perception and thought". In *Image and environment: Cognitive mapping and spatial behavior*, edited by Downs R M. and D. Stea, 63-78. Chicago: Aldine.

Kitchen, Ted. 2001. "Planning in response to terrorism: The case of Manchester, England." *Journal of Architectural and Planning Research*, 18 (4): 325-340.

Lang, Jon. 1987. *Creating architectural theory: The role of the behavioral sciences in environmental design*. New York: Van Nostrand Reinhold.

Nasar, Jack L. 1997. "New developments in aesthetics for urban design." In *Advances in environment, behavior, and design*, edited by Gary T. Moore and Robert W. Marans, 149-193. New York: Plenum Press.

Nasar, Jack L. and Kym M. Jones. 1997. "Landscapes of fear and stress." *Environment and Behavior*, 29 (3): 291-323.

Newman, Oscar. 1972. *Defensible space: Crime prevention through urban design*. New York: The Macmillan Company.

Orians, Gordon H. 1980. "Habitat selection: General theory and applications to human behavior." In *The evolution of human social behavior*, edited by Joan S. Lockard, 49-66. New York: Elsevier.

Orians, Gordon H. 1986. "An ecological and evolutionary approach to landscape aesthetics." In *Meanings and values in landscape*, edited by Edmund Penning-Roswell and David Lowenthal, 3-25. London: Allen & Unwin.

Rabinowitz, C. and R. Coughlin. 1970. "Analysis of landscape characteristics relevant to preference." In *Regional Science Research Institute: Discussion Paper Series no.38*. Philadelphia: Regional Science Research Institute.

Ruiz, J. and Bernaldez, F. 1982. "Landscape perception by its traditional users: The ideal landscape of Madrid livestock raisers." *Landscape Planning*, 9: 279-297.

Saarinen, Thomas F. 1976. *Environmental planning: Perception and behavior*. Boston: Houghton Mifflin.

Seidel, Andrew D. and Taner Ozdil. Forthcoming. "The knowledge needs of architects: International comparisons." *Journal of Architectural Education*.

Shaffer, Garnett S. and L. M. Anderson. 1983. "Perceptions of the security and attractiveness of urban parking lots." *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 5: 311-323.

Stamps III, Arthur E. 1997. "A paradigm for distinguishing significant from nonsignificant visual impacts: Theory, implementation, case histories." *Environmental Impact Assessment Review*, 17 (4). New York: Elsevier Science Inc.

Tijerino, Roger. 1998. "Civil spaces: A critical perspective of defensible space." *Journal of Architectural and Planning Research*, 15 (4): 321-37.

Ulrich, Roger S. 1993. "Biophilia, biophobia, and natural landscapes." In *The biophilia hypothesis*, edited by Stephen R. Kellert and Edward O. Wilson, 73-137. Washington, DC: Island Press.

Ulrich, Roger S., R. Simons, B. Losito, E. Fiorito, M. Miles and M. Zelson. 1991. "Stress recovery during exposure to natural and urban environments." *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 11: 201-230.

Wright, Andrew G., ed. 2002, 2003. *Building for a secure future*, Special reports by Engineering News-Record & Architectural Record. McGraw-Hill Cos.

Ms. Gali Zilbershtein is a PhD student in the Department of Architecture, College of Architecture, Texas A&M University. Ms. Zilbershtein had received her B.Sc. in Architecture and City Planning from the Technion, Israel Institute of Technology, graduating *Summa Cum Laude*, June, 2001. In January 2002 she began attending the PhD program at A&M University. For the academic year 2003-2004, she has been awarded the William Wayne Caudill Research Fellowship by the Department of Architecture, Texas A&M University, for the best dissertation proposal "Architecture in the Era of Terror: Design, Perception of Security and Behavioral Propensity". In addition, Ms. Zilbershtein was awarded the Best Overall Project Award at the College's Graduate Research Student Symposium, April 2003.

Professor Dr. Andrew D. Seidel is a professor of Landscape Architecture and Urban Planning and of Architecture at the College of Architecture, Texas A&M University. He earned his PhD from the University of Michigan (1980), Masters from Harvard University (1974), and Bachelor of Architecture from Pratt Institute (1972). His areas of interest include environmental design, planning methods and techniques, computer applications and the relationship between public policy and physical design. Professor Seidel has published 12 books and over 65 articles. He is also the Editor-in-Chief of the Journal of Architectural and Planning Research (1980 - present). Currently, professor Seidel is teaching graduate seminars on survey of human behavior and design and on scholarly publication in planning and architecture.